

**An exploratory comprehensive media study and review of tribal
communities of Jharkhand: Ethno - Herbs, Shrubs and Medicinal Plants
perspective**

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The State of Jharkhand is blessed with immense biodiversity, moderate climate, rich cultural and historical heritage, religious places of worship and ethnic aspects to make the State the ultimate destination for bio-scientists & tourists. The lush green forests, rivers and waterfalls of this primeval land are home to many kinds of spectacular flora and fauna. Age-old tribes are the major inhabitants of Jharkhand dominated by tribals (32 tribal community) enriched in terms of cultural heritage and natural resources includes minerals and biodiversity. The wide range of herbs, shrubs and medicinal plants are seen here, to which tribal and local peoples have a lot of acquaintance. However, the medicinal value and conservation of such natural resources needs to be addressed as many of these plants are used for prevention and treatment of various diseases by traditional practitioners and healers since ancient times. Our present review focuses on documentation of ethno-medicinal herbs, shrubs and medicinal plants that can be used for further research through the lens of media.

Keywords: Ethno Medicinal Knowledge, Acquaintance, Nutrient composition, Ethnic Community of Jharkhand, Media